

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THREE ASPECTS OF PAUL RICOEURS TRANSLATION PARADIGM

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Abstract

The modern challenges faced by the global community, particularly the increasing interdependence in the global information sphere, necessitate the search for languages for international communication and new translation strategies. The issue of translation has always been relevant, and today it is perceived as a philosophical problem due to the crisis of communication and understanding. Of particular interest is Paul Ricoeur's conceptual approach to translation, based on his latest works on translational issues, which are a logical continuation of his exploration of the problem of understanding. He focuses on the hermeneutic and general philosophical meaning of the problem in question. This paper examines the linguistic, anthropological, and hermeneutic aspects of Ricoeur's translation paradigm. Defining these three aspects of Ricoeur's translation paradigm allows for an understanding of the structural regularities of translation as a creative process linked to the translator's worldview and creative potential. An analysis of real translation practice suggests the possibility of translation not just from one language to another but also the provision of the general communicative function of spiritual culture, opportunities for interpretation, and narrative. To achieve the set goal, general scientific research methods were used, including the comparative method. An analysis of the three aspects of Ricoeur's translation theory showed that such an approach is an objective, comprehensive way to understand the problems of translation as both a linguistic activity and a cultural and interpretive endeavor.

The contribution of Western philosophers to the issue of translation is invaluable, allowing us to recognize the complexities of translation from a Western worldview perspective. As a result of the activities of philosophers like Schleiermacher, Benjamin, Derrida, and Ricoeur, who engaged in direct active translation practice, there was a paradigm shift in translation. A transition occurred from an ethnocentric to an ethical paradigm of translation. Schleiermacher, formulating translation conditions, emphasized the necessity of different approaches for different texts. These conditions should ensure the fidelity of the translation to the original text. Walter Benjamin introduced the idea of a pure language, considering it the sole capacity of translation. Ricoeur's contribution to translation theory can be viewed in several key points. For Ricoeur, translation, like all understanding, is an act of interpretation. He saw translation as a process in which the interpreter encounters the "other" in the form of a text in the source language and tries to recreate this "other" in the target language. Ricoeur asserted that translation also has an ethical dimension since it involves recognition and respect for the "other". Translators should aim for a just representation of the original text, preserving its meaning and intentions. Ricoeur acknowledged that complete equivalence between the source and target texts is impossible. However, he believed that a translator can and should strive for the highest possible accuracy. Ricoeur made a distinction between understanding (interpretation) and explanation (analytical breakdown). This distinction becomes particularly relevant in translation, as the translator must not only "explain" the text but also "understand" it. Ricoeur viewed translation as a bridge between cultures through which people can achieve mutual understanding despite linguistic and cultural barriers. Ricoeur made an invaluable contribution to addressing the translation problem, which remains relevant in philosophical discourse.

Keywords: Paul Ricoeur, translation paradigm, hermeneutics, linguistic hospitality, narrative.

Introduction. Modern philosophical research reflects the contradictory problems of translation, its cultural, philosophical, and linguistic aspects awaiting solutions. This indicates that the issue of translation, in the context of globalization and multiculturalism of the modern world, remains quite relevant.

Overall, the problem of translation is one of the complex challenges faced not only by philosophers but also linguists, writers, cultural researchers, machine language creators, and so forth. At first glance, the problem of translation might seem purely linguistic, addressing the tasks of how to convey the meaning of a word or phrase in another language while preserving its original sense. It's known that every language embodies

a unique worldview and a specific cultural context, making the task of translation even more challenging. It's also connected with questions about the nature of language, human ability to comprehend and interpret information, and the problem of how feasible it is to understand another person's thinking or perception of another culture.

In today's world, becoming increasingly globalized and multicultural, the problem of translation gains new facets. For instance, challenges arise about how to convey the cultural nuances of a particular social phenomenon or process in an era of rapid mass information dissemination through the internet, and so forth. Paul

Ricoeur's examination of the translation problem represents a multifaceted and profound study in the domain of language philosophy and hermeneutics. In the modern world, which is ever more globalized and multicultural, issues of translation and mutual understanding become exceedingly pertinent. Understanding Ricoeur's approach might aid in finding ways for harmonious interaction among diverse cultures. Ricoeur views translation as an act of hospitality, which could form the basis for discussing ethical aspects of translation in modern conditions, especially in the context of international relations, migration, and global dialogue. With the advancement of artificial intelligence and machine translation, new challenges emerge for understanding what constitutes a good translation. Reflecting on Ricoeur's philosophical approaches can offer deep insights into these problems. Investigating Ricoeur's perspective on the translation issue can further the understanding of his overall hermeneutic approach, which is relevant for a wide array of questions in philosophy, sociology, and cultural studies. For professionals in the fields of translation and linguistics, studying Ricoeur's methodologies can offer novel perspectives and approaches to their work based on philosophical principles.

The earliest mentions of translation can be found in ancient texts. The ancient Egyptians translated religious texts, while the ancient Greeks turned to translations when interacting with other cultures. Roman scholars and writers, such as Cicero and Horace, pondered the principles of translation. The Middle Ages were also a time of translating the scientific and philosophical works of Arab scholars into Latin. Erasmus of Rotterdam discussed principles and methods of translation. The 20th century witnessed a real explosion in the development of translation theory, especially thanks to the works of scholars like R. Jakobson, E. Levitsky, and W. Benjamin. Numerous new approaches, methods, and strategies for translation were proposed. The issues of literary translation are deeply intertwined with culture, history, sociology, psychology, and, of course, philosophy. The philosophy of translation addresses questions such as the nature of language, the relationship between the author and the translator, and the place of the text in culture. In a philosophical context, translation is not just a transmission of meaning; it's an act of communication between cultures, times, and individuals. Thus, the theory of translation in the context of philosophy is not only a practical activity but also profound contemplation about the nature of human language, culture, and communication.

Issues of translation are also explored in such modern philosophical movements as analytic philosophy, hermeneutics, structuralism, and post-structuralism. These translation approaches differ because they are based on different foundational philosophical assumptions.

For instance, in his essay "On the Different Methods of Translation", F. Schleiermacher focuses on two types of translations: one that brings the author closer to the reader, and another that brings the reader closer to the author. Schleiermacher favors the latter approach, arguing that the best translation is the one that

makes the reader feel another culture and language. Through his contemplation on translation, Schleiermacher aims to preserve the uniqueness of the original text without sacrificing its spirit [Schleiermacher, 2002; 82]. W. von Humboldt believed that language is not just a means of communication but reflects the national spirit, culture, and worldview of a people. He believed that each language is unique and carries its own perception of the world. This perspective contrasted with the prevailing view at the time that saw language as a universal communication tool. For Humboldt, language actively participates in the thinking process, not just serving as its tool [Lipps 1976; 85].

Willard Van Orman Quine, in his work "Word and Object", posits the idea that a precise translation between two languages is impossible due to the lack of unique correspondence between their words and sentences. Hermeneutics, as the art of understanding and interpreting texts, often grapples with translation problems. Jacques Derrida, a post-structuralist, studied questions of translation, focusing on how language determines and generates meaning. He argued that language has inherent contradictions that make the task of translation especially challenging [Derrida J., 1987].

Walter Benjamin [Benjamin, 1972] in his essay "The Task of the Translator" views translation as a form of art and asserts that true translation maintains the "pure linguistic essence" of the original. Umberto Eco, a writer, and philosopher, also touched upon translation matters in his works, especially the intricacies and nuances of translating literary works [Eco, 2013]. George Steiner, a renowned scholar in the realm of translation, endeavors to present the evolution of theoretical perspectives on translation in his book "After Babel" [Steiner, 1975]. His exploration of translation is based on deep philosophical and cultural analysis, acknowledging the complexity and multifaceted nature of this activity.

The aim of this article is to examine and analyze three key aspects of Paul Ricoeur's translation paradigm, namely the linguistic, anthropological, and hermeneutical, to unveil the philosophical foundations of his approach and determine their role and significance in contemporary translation theory and practice.

The following research methods were employed: a critical analysis of primary sources, which will provide a deep understanding of Ricoeur's views; a comparative method, juxtaposing Ricoeur's views on translation with other philosophical and linguistic approaches to the topic; and a historical-philosophical method, facilitating an examination of the development of translation concepts in the broad context of the history of philosophy and culture, aiming to define Ricoeur's place in this evolution. These methods will enable the article's author to conduct a profound and comprehensive analysis of Ricoeur's translation paradigm, its foundations, and its influence on modern understandings of translation.

The emergence of the modern paradigm of translation. The problem of translation begins after Babel (the myth of the Tower of Babel, where after the Great Flood, people began to speak in many lan-

guages), so to speak, with the spread of an insurmountable diversity of languages [Steiner, 1975]. The proliferation of languages poses the threat that people might not be able to communicate with each other, and it seems that in response to this threat arises the desire and need to translate. There is a long history of philosophical debates on the conceptual question of how translation is even possible [Ricoeur, 2004: 27]. From the history of philosophy, scholars were guided by two diametrically opposed alternatives. On the one hand, the diversity of languages is perceived by some as something radically heterogeneous. For instance, in the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, it is argued that different linguistic systems cannot be superimposed onto one another due to the differences between their phonetic, syntactic, or semantic subdivisions. These structural differences between linguistic systems parallel cognitive differences between the speakers of two languages, implying that the structure of one's native language heavily influences or even entirely determines one's worldview. Since each language turns out to form its separate, self-sufficient, and incomparable unique system, translation is considered a priori impossible. However, at the other speculative extreme, the emphasis is placed on explaining the actual existence of translation. Starting from this point, attempts are made to return to how translation is possible. In this endeavor, some authors propose the hypothesis of an original language from which all natural languages can trace their origin, like the myth of the Tower of Babel, while others seek to perfect a universal code, such as the logically perfect language described by G. Leibniz. Yet instead of chasing either of these speculative extremes, Ricoeur suggests setting aside this theoretical question of translation with its alternatives of complete untranslatability and full translatability. Instead, his explanation of translation is guided by the practical dialectic of "fidelity and betrayal," encountered in the real practice of translation.

To navigate within the framework of this dialectic, let's first turn to the etymology of the word translation. The English word "translate" originates from the Latin "transfere", which means to transfer. The French word "traducteur", although it has a Latin root, comes from another verb, "traducere", meaning to lead across. Thus, the etymology of the word suggests that it is analogous to trade activity, where the translator is like a merchant transferring idea from one language to another. However, to complicate this overly simplified model, it is essential to note that this transfer or exchange doesn't happen without causing a shift or transformation in what is being transferred.

It is noteworthy that the Latin root for translation, "traducere", also underlies the English verb "to traduce", which relates to the act of slanderous or defamatory statements. This suggests that translation does not merely replace one word with another but rather is a kind of betrayal of the original word. In translation, "traditore" means to betray. Doesn't this etymological duality of the translator as both a merchant and a betrayer tell us about the fate of translation, namely, that fidelity and betrayal are inseparable?

The dialectic of fidelity and betrayal is inevitable because the translator serves two masters. Translation

is a model of mediation, where the translator builds a bridge to connect two poles and facilitate communication. On one hand, there's the work, the author, and their language, and on the other, the reader of the translated text. In the middle stands the translator, as a true hermeneutic and intermediary, conveying the message from one language to another, striving to address diverse demands. We can echo F. Schleiermacher in saying that the translator should bring the "reader to the author", upholding their "oath of fidelity", and yet, at the same time, the translator must bring the "author to the reader" [Schleiermacher, 1992: 42]. The translator must work to overcome resistances from both poles in question, achieving a kind of interlingual and intercultural reconciliation.

In this context, the primary challenge for the translator is to confront the resistance created by the text being translated. The text becomes an expression of an alien reality, which does not wish to be distorted and seeks to be conscientiously mediated. It resists any form of conveyance so strongly that it sometimes claims its own untranslatability. Secondly, the translator also must overcome the resistance of the reader of the text, that is, the resistance of the language into which the text should be translated. This veneration of one's native language, combined with a heightened sense of self-sufficiency, gives birth to linguistic ethnocentrism and cultural hegemony.

In both cases, translation becomes an act of overcoming these forms of resistance based on the concept of identity. Antoine Berman aptly describes this dual resistance and considers the translator's efforts to be ambivalent. The translator seeks to act in two directions: they wish to make their language take responsibility for another language and make the other language adopt the matter of our language [Berman, 1995].

Translation executes a form of mediation that transcends the enclosure provided by two different linguistic universals; translation stands at a crossroads where claims to identity are softened, and any potential tension that might exist between the original text and the reader, with their diverse cultural identities, is alleviated.

The Linguistic Aspect of Translation in the Understanding of P. Ricoeur

Paul Ricoeur is one of the most prominent influential French philosophers of the XX century. His work covers a broad range of philosophical topics, including hermeneutics, phenomenology, ethics, and more. Ricoeur began his academic career studying phenomenology. His early works were influenced by philosophers like Edmund Husserl and Martin Heidegger. Over time, Ricoeur became a key figure in the development of hermeneutics or the theory of interpretation. His interest in texts and their interpretation led to the formulation of a complex hermeneutic philosophy. Ricoeur is also known for his works where he analyzed the formation of human experience and self-understanding influenced by narratives. In his later works, he delved into issues of ethics. Ricoeur also explored religious texts and symbols, trying to understand the mechanisms conveying profound truths about human experience. In his later works, Ricoeur continued to probe the relationship

between language, text, and interpretation. Paul Ricoeur also proposes a different paradigm for translation.

Let's consider each of the three aspects of the translation paradigm he suggested. The linguistic level concerns the very act of translation, the process of conveying meaning from one language to another. Here, Ricoeur recognizes all the complexities and nuances associated with the misalignment of linguistic structures, idioms, and cultural references.

Full realization of the principle of translatability is impossible. In this sense, there's no criterion that could establish a good translation, because there's no "third text" [Ricoeur, 2006: 7] between the original and the translation, i.e., there's no other text that could bear the true meaning, and therefore, be a judgment criterion to check if the translator really says the same as the author of the original text. From this perspective, we can ask: is it conceivable that there is a perfect and original language, that there are universal and common linguistic structures that all "translation efforts" would ideally aim for?

There are no forms of a "linguistic absolute" [Ricoeur, 2006;9] of a universal language that could fully bridge the distance between itself and the other. The form of a linguistic absolute, according to Ricoeur, is the cosmopolitan dream of the Enlightenment era about creating a universal library, containing all translations in all languages. The goal of this ideal is to "fill the interlinguistic space of communication and make up for the lack of a universal language" [Ricoeur, 2006;8].

The linguistic absolute is also the ideal of a pure language, which, as in the case of Walter Benjamin, represents a messianic echo that every translation should contain within itself [Benjamin, 1972]. These ideals of linguistic absoluteness and perfect translation arise from universalist and pluralist stances and aim not to absolutize one's own language, but paradoxically lead to the oblivion of both the other and one's own language. Those who adopt this linguistic universalism lose their roots [Ricoeur, 2006: 9].

What else is involved in the act of translation? It arises from the desire to overcome the unease that might be induced by the presence of the other. Translators can only continue to seek some form of equivalence between languages, rather than establishing definitive correspondences; they can only identify possible semantic and linguistic transitions from one language to another. The act of translation requires constant review, as Ricoeur writes: "A good translation aims only for a presumed equivalence, not based on a demonstrable identity of meaning. Equivalence without identity. This equivalence can only be sought, refined, assumed, and the only way to criticize a translation is to offer another, better one" [Ricoeur, 2006: 21].

Between two texts, that is, the original and the translation, there can only be equivalence, but not complete adaptation and full correspondence, as it happens between this and that, between the original and the translated text; one cannot be reduced to the other. And precisely this impossibility becomes the condition of the possibility of any future translation. "The insurmountable status of the dialogicity of the act of translation" is the necessary background of translation itself

[Ricoeur, 2006: 9]. A perfect translation would correspond to the exhaustion of the impulse to translate, and thus, to the interruption of the desire for dialogue.

If there was a perfect translation, there would be perfect understanding, and where there is perfect understanding, the dialogical impulse fades. In this sense, it can be argued that the act of translation may point to both the finitude of analysis and understanding, as well as the additional cognitive resources of a person. From here, we can conclude that if the act of translation is based on the original anthropological-existential structure, the will to translate cannot be eliminated by itself. Accepting the loss of an absolute translation is the premise of translation itself. This is what paradoxically makes possible the "translation as a source of happiness" [Ricoeur, 2006: 3].

In translation, there's both a preservation of loss and an "agreement" to loss. This "work of mourning" consists not only in renouncing the "very ideal of a perfect translation" but also in subjecting oneself to the "test by the other." In the essay "The Challenge and Happiness of Translation," Ricoeur makes some remarks about the "great difficulties and small joys" of translation. The "great difficulties" of translation are expressed in the word "épreuve", found in Antoine Berman's book "L'épreuve de l'étranger", and has a dual meaning: "endured punishment" or "test" [Berman, 1992]. Ricoeur compares this "test" to what Walter Benjamin calls the "task of the translator". This task has a dual meaning given by S. Freud when he talks about the "work of memory" and the "work of mourning" [Ricoeur, 2004: 15].

But from which perfect translation must one renounce? It is the dream of an ideal translation. The ideal translation is one that represents a "gain without losses." It is what would like to take the place of the universal language. However, it is precisely this mourning of the absolute translation that explains the happiness of translation. The happiness of translation is an acquisition, when, having agreed with the loss of an absolute translation, it accepts the gap between adequacy and equivalence. Recognizing the irreducibility of the author to the reader, the translator finds happiness in what Ricoeur likes to call linguistic hospitality. Ricoeur adds, "linguistic hospitality is also a model for exchange between religions and cultures" [Ricoeur, 2006;19,43]. Linguistic hospitality, as the pleasure of living another's language, is compensated by the pleasure of receiving the word of another in one's own home [Ricoeur, 2006;20].

Thus, translation acts as a form of mediation, marked by its constitutive, universal yet pluralistic openness to communication: there are two main reasons for this act of mediation. Firstly, while everyone speaks, they do so in different languages; in reality, there's no single universal language but many idioms. Secondly, even though there can never be a universal common language, different languages are not so foreign to each other that they cannot be translated.

Anthropological Aspect in P. Ricoeur's Translation Theory. According to Ricoeur, translation is also a process of encountering the "other". When we translate, we face not only a different language but also

a different culture, a different world, and a different value system. In this context, translation becomes a way of broadening our horizons and integrating the cultural wealth of other people into our personal experience.

Ricoeur points out that it is possible to translate not only languages but also cultures. The starting point of Ricoeur's research is his amazement at the fact of cultural plurality and a deep belief in the value of humanity. Indeed, there are different cultures, languages, nations, and religions. But while the word "cultures" is plural, the term "humanity" is singular. The challenge is to determine the value we can attribute to humanity: on one hand, the human being is a unique entity; on the other, they are part of the human community.

Translation is a response to the undeniable phenomenon of human plurality. It acts as a mediator between cultural plurality and the unity of humanity. A common interpretation of the myth of the Tower of Babel suggests that the colossal biblical tower is an emblem of disorder, a mixture of languages, and consequently, a lack of communication among people due to the lost single "paradise language" [Ricoeur, 2006: 12]. However, this myth can be understood differently. It might be that the Babel multilingualism is not a divine curse, i.e., a result of the wrath and vengeance of gods. It's possible to see linguistic diversity and the resulting non-communicability not just as a defeat, but also as an opportunity. Ricoeur offers a more favorable interpretation of the Babel myth. It's not a "linguistic catastrophe inflicted by a jealous God upon humans," but rather an initial state of division. Thus, Babel is "not a metaphor for the moment of our becoming, but the condition of our starting point" [Henaff, Marcel, 2006;69].

The need for translation, ever-present throughout human history, reveals an inherent ability to study and practice languages different from our own. The multiplicity of languages represents the rich tapestry of human life and worlds as interpreted and communicated linguistically. Translation ensures that humanity isn't viewed as something undifferentiated; it allows languages to coexist, exchange meanings, and amplify the potentials inherent in them. The confusion of Babel can be interpreted not so much as a catastrophe ordained by God, but as a portrayal of the potential of languages. Babel isn't a condemnation but a stimulus for reflection [Ricoeur, 2006;34-36].

For Ricoeur, the emergence of translation has always run parallel to the evolution of language diversity. But it cannot be reduced to a mere technique spontaneously used by "travelers, merchants..." [Ricoeur, 2004: 21] prior to the advent of professional translators. Translation is permissible within concrete universals, not those abstracted from history. Thus, the act of translation serves the human project, which knows how to remain plural.

Pluralistic thinking necessitates turning to cultural universals, historically localized, whose translation helps preserve them. Translation sustains plurality. In translating, we create a space for linguistic hospitality. In this way, the practice of translation becomes a tangible example of hospitable space in the linguistic domain. According to Ricoeur, translation is closely

linked to other forms of mutual hospitality between cultures.

Linguistic hospitality implies a possible model for intercultural interaction. Indeed, intercultural communication requires "translators from culture to culture" [Ricoeur, 1996: 5]. In the context of intercultural dialogue, a truly critical yet peaceful discussion is possible only by following a hermeneutic path. To engage in a dialogue with other perspectives, efforts must be made to manifest self-criticism, agreeing to step outside oneself and recognize one's own fallibility and incompleteness. There's a need to restore the concept of hospitality, which primarily means having diverse beliefs. Thus, it becomes possible to engage in a concrete dialogue, an exchange that happens akin to translation, through continuous processes of mutual enrichment.

Ricoeur's strategy was to outline two distinct approaches to the challenge of translation. Translation not only has an interlingual dimension but also an intralingual one. Intralingual translation is more than just a process where words from one language are rendered into another. In intralingual translation, we distance ourselves from our native language and view it as any other language. Reflecting upon our own language, we come to see it as foreign. Here, we confront what we might also encounter in interlingual translation.

One might assume that for speakers of the same language, the task of translation is unnecessary. They can express their thoughts and wishes simply because they speak the same language. However, there's a difference between the ideal of a perfect language, where every word can only have one meaning, and the reality where each word can have multiple meanings. This linguistic diversity creates a need for translation even within a single linguistic community, even in daily communication between people using the same language.

It can be said that a common language is a necessary but not sufficient condition for understanding. The need for intralingual translation is clear. Of course, this problem doesn't only arise from the diversity of terms but also from differences in age, gender, race, and social status, which can hinder understanding between people. In such cases, one might be asked to rephrase or modify what they've said. Here, the act of translation occurs within a single language, and both external and internal translation allows one word to be swapped for another, i.e., replacing one sign with another to convey the same thing differently.

According to hermeneutic philosophers, language allows us to know ourselves. Similarly, as we use it to express our thoughts, it must be acknowledged that language shapes what and how we think. But this transition isn't always smooth. Sometimes we get carried away by the spoken words and find that we didn't express what we intended. Between what was said and what one wanted to say, the uttered words become something other than their own, feeling alien to the speaker's intent.

Octavio Paz sheds light on this when he ties this process to mastering the language itself, noting that as we learn to speak, we simultaneously learn to translate. Paz points out that children translate their experiences

into a language that gradually becomes their own and that we are all engaged in this process. This perspective suggests that translation isn't merely a secondary phenomenon in language; it's part of the initial acquisition of the language itself [Paz, 1992; 152]. Начало формы

Based on what has been said about intralingual translation, we can draw some significant conclusions that naturally arise from text theory, but which Ricœur never makes explicit in his work. It's impossible to conceptualize translation merely in terms of interlingual translation, where the task would be to transmit a pure or original text to a foreign language, which would be a secondary text. It's evident that the so-called original text is initially engaged in a translation activity. An author's effort to communicate with a reader in the same language can primarily be characterized from the viewpoint of intralingual translation.

What the author attempts to do is provide the reader with a new understanding of what is familiar by saying the same thing differently. However, a similar struggle also takes place within the author themselves. An author never fully possesses their words. There's a continuous battle to find the right words to convey a particular thought or experience. In this respect, the author's work closely resembles that of a translator, both in search of the right word or equivalent to convey another word or experience that could be expressed in another language.

Ricœur's approach to translation began by setting aside the theoretical question of what makes translation possible and turned to the practical dialectic of fidelity and betrayal guiding the actual translation work. One could argue that translating a text from one language to another is feasible because the text's author is initially involved in intralingual translation activity. That is, any text is already a translated text.

The Hermeneutic Aspect of P. Ricœur's Translation Theory. This is perhaps the deepest and most multifaceted part of P. Ricœur's paradigm. Hermeneutics studies the process of interpreting texts, and when translating, we always interpret a text. According to Ricœur, a translator doesn't merely convey meaning but also explores, interprets, and, in a way, recreates the text in a new context. This process requires a profound immersion into the source text, as well as an awareness of the translator's position concerning the text.

Ricœur presents arguments that contradict the structuralist perception of language as a neutral system of rules and signs. In disputing the structuralist understanding of language as a system, Ricœur advances the idea that discourse isn't a static system but, more likely, occurs as a necessary event at a specific moment in time [Ricoeur, 1976].

Language is actively used and only makes sense in specific contexts and interactions with speakers, writers, readers, or listeners. Ricœur suggests that language has a collective nature, owing to the participation and agreement of many people, and it represents a set of rules and norms shared by members of a particular linguistic community. Thus, language is shaped and evolves within society.

Language is anonymous in the sense that it doesn't depend on the intentions of individual people. This

means that no one can claim to possess a language in some special way, and that language exists independently of the specific intentions or desires of individual individuals. Language is unconscious from the standpoint of the structural or cultural unconscious. This means that much of our communication at the language level happens without our awareness, and we use language without thinking about its structure or historical roots [Ricoeur, 1976].

At the same time, discourse represents a temporal event in language. Discourse, as an event in language, has several characteristics. Discourse always occurs at a specific time, in the present. Language is an object placed outside of time. This means that the act of communication is momentary and depends on the context and time in which it occurs. Ricœur views language itself as an object existing outside of time and independent of specific acts of communication. Discourse is self-referential, i.e., discourse relates to itself and the speaker. In discourse, personal pronouns and other indicators are used that point to the speaker and the addressee. This makes discourse more individual and linked to a specific participant in communication. Ricœur notes that discourse refers to something external. Discourse always relates to something outside of itself. Language, on the other hand, relates to signs placed within the same system. Unlike language, which operates with signs and rules within a system, discourse is always connected to a world that can be described. Thus, discourse serves as a means of conveying information and interacting with the external world. Ricœur emphasizes that the participants in the discourse to whom the message is addressed are also part of the discourse itself [Ricoeur, 1974]. This means that the interaction between participants and their responses or reactions influence the course of the discourse, and they also become part of it.

According to Ricœur, language cannot be reduced to unambiguous meanings, as it is in language that ambiguity is reflected, and therefore approaching language always requires hermeneutic interpretive activity, necessarily preceding understanding. Ricœur asserts that language is inherently ambiguous and contains various meanings. It cannot be reduced to unambiguous and absolute values. This is because language is a product of culture and society, meaning its values and meanings can change depending on the context and interpretation.

Understanding and approaching language, according to Ricœur, always requires hermeneutic interpretive activity. Ricœur believed that interpretation is an integral part of the understanding process, and that every act of communication requires interpretation to reveal meanings. Ricœur also emphasized the importance of preliminary understanding that participants in communication bring with them. This preliminary understanding influences how they interpret language and discourse. It is important to recognize that every individual comes to communication with their own notions and experiences that shape their interpretation of language.

Thus, according to Ricœur, language is not a static and unambiguous system, but rather an ambiguous and

changeable means of communication. To understand language and its meanings, interpretation is always required, which depends on context and preliminary understanding. These ideas became essential components of modern hermeneutic studies in linguistics and philosophy [Ricoeur, 1976: 33]. The necessity of hermeneutic activity within his theory stems from the definition of language as a system of symbols, where symbols can have various meanings, including both direct and literal, as well as indirect and metaphorical meanings. This multitude of possible meanings makes language ambiguous and implies the need for interpretation [Ricoeur, 1978: 98].

Translation activity, aimed not only at achieving equivalence but also at creating a translational function in the target linguoculture, necessarily requires the use of such a hermeneutic method that challenges any primary meaning of the lexeme and leads to the identification of its secondary meanings, their specific expression, both in the source and in the target languages. Based on the above, it follows that hermeneutic activity is present throughout the entire translation activity, rather than just being its initial stage.

Interpretation as an essential part of the hermeneutic method represents a dynamic process, involving both the methodological moment of understanding and the methodological moment of explanation [Ricoeur, 1991: 152].

In Ricoeur's theory, hermeneutic understanding is conceptualized as one of the essential determinations of a person and, therefore, as a method by which one not only grasps concepts but can also interpret them in context. Hermeneutics allows the translator to explore the axiological aspects of the text and convey them in the target language and culture.

Ricoeur's hermeneutic method consists of three stages: prefiguration, configuration, and refiguration. Prefiguration stage. This stage represents the initial phase in which an individual possesses unarticulated knowledge about their cultural environment and language. This stage can also be described as the one where a person operates with all their knowledge, pragmatic language, and experience, not yet structured to solve a specific cognitive-reflective task [Ricoeur, 1984: 19].

As for the thematic and non-thematic cognitive abilities of each person, a translator, as a professional user of at least two languages, possesses cognitive-reflective knowledge in which at least two linguocultures are intertwined and intersect. At the intra-lingual and inter-lingual levels of hermeneutic activity, it should be noted that in interpretation and understanding, an individual not only uses language but also modifies and transforms it.

As Taylor asserts, language is not just a set of individual tools; it is networked and constitutes a single whole in each of its parts. People constantly shape the language, expand the boundaries of expression, create new terms, move old ones, and give the language an altered range of meanings [Taylor, 1985].

Configuration stage. This is the stage of semantic conceptualization in the language. From exploring the pre-narrative scheme to configuring events and plots,

we may need to go through two phases: eventalization, use, and conceptualization [Ricoeur, 1984: 12].

Eventalization is the process of identifying and representing events and actions implied or described in the text. At this stage, the translator analyzes the text to highlight events, actions, motives, agents (characters performing actions), circumstances, and other elements that make up the plot or moral content of the text. Eventalization allows the translator to "unlock" semantic elements and make them visible for further interpretation and transfer in the target text.

After the eventalization phase, the translator proceeds to the next step - use and conceptualization. At this stage, the translator forms a semantic concept based on the identified events and elements of the text. This involves selecting linguistic and structural means to convey meaning and create a similar semantic experience in the target text. Thus, the translator not only transfers words from one language to another but also transplants meaning and events into a new linguocultural environment [Ricoeur, 1984: 17].

The third stage, refiguration, represents a complete understanding of the discourse and its interpretation. At the refiguration stage, the world of the text and the world of the reader overlap. Hermeneutic activity is fully realized in reading, which represents the space between pragmatics and semantic structure. Ricoeur's hermeneutic method of understanding and interpreting the text represents a shift in translation theory from focusing on the concept of hermeneutic understanding and analysis of the three stages of the hermeneutic interpretation process [Ricoeur, 1984: 33].

However, when it comes to exploring possible translation approaches and achieving an optimal balance between equivalence to the source text, functionality, and translation adequacy, Ricoeur's theory has weaknesses. Ricoeur asserts that once the text is written, the author loses control, and new relationships are established between the text and the reader in the appropriation process. The text is open not only for an infinite number of readings but also for an infinite number of interpretations. Applying such an approach to translation can also lead to a situation where the meaning of the source text in the translation activity, as an interpretative activity, will be lost.

Undoubtedly, translation cannot become a space for an unlimited number of interpretations. The boundaries of meaning and form transfer, on the one hand, and the functionality and appropriateness of the target text, on the other, limit translation creativity. For the translator to achieve such a balance in their work, hermeneutic activity is required throughout the entire translation process, not just at its initial stage.

Conclusion

Translation is a complex and multifaceted process where linguistic and cultural barriers aim to be overcome to convey meaning. The paradigm of translation in the philosophy of Paul Ricoeur offers a profound and enriching way of understanding translation challenges not just as linguistic, but also as cultural and interpretative activities. Relying on Ricoeur's work, we realize that the ideal of a complete and absolute translation

without loss cannot be achieved. Structures of languages, cultural nuances, and idiomatic expressions make translation a task requiring not just linguistic but also cultural sensitivity. From this, the act of translation can be viewed as an attempt to bridge the foreignness of another language, striving for equivalents, but not all absolute correspondences. It's an art demanding compromises and acknowledgment that some aspects might be lost or distorted. However, despite all the complexities and challenges translators face, the process of translation brings joy and satisfaction. This joy arises from the "linguistic hospitality" - the opportunity to delve into another language and culture and invite the other into one's world. Translation isn't just transferring words from one language to another. It's an act of cultural and linguistic mediation, where perfect equivalence might be unattainable, but efforts toward this ideal enrich both cultures and lead to a deeper understanding of the essence of language.

Translation stands as a response to the undeniable phenomenon of human plurality. It acts as a mediator between the diversity of cultures and the unity of humanity. The need for translation, ever-present in human history, reveals an innate capacity to learn and practice languages other than one's own. The plurality of languages expresses the richness of human life forms and worlds, interpreted, and conveyed linguistically. Translation ensures humanity isn't viewed as something undifferentiated; it allows languages to coexist, exchange meanings, and expand their inherent potentials. Plural thinking turns to culturally localized universals, whose translation helps preserve them. Ricoeur sidestepped the theoretical question of what makes translation possible and turned to the practical dialectics of fidelity and betrayal that guide the real work of translation.

The hermeneutic aspect of Ricoeur's translation paradigm is the most multifaceted and profound. Ricoeur's philosophy concerning language and hermeneutics embodies the complexity and ambiguity of human communication. By emphasizing the polysemy of language and the importance of interpretation, Ricoeur pushes us towards a deeper and more responsible approach to understanding texts and speech. His ideas assert that understanding cannot be reduced to a mere transmission of information; it's a process involving active interaction between the sender and the receiver, their contexts, and prior experiences. Hermeneutic interpretation, according to Ricoeur, goes beyond mere decoding of linguistic symbols. It's the art of unveiling profound meanings which might be hidden or ambiguous. This deep and reflective practice enables the crossing of cultural and linguistic boundaries, enriching our comprehension of the world and our place within it. Therefore, Ricoeur's theory on language and hermeneutics provides us with tools for profound and meaningful communication. It reminds us that language is not just a tool, but a cultural heritage, rich in meanings and interpretations, requiring our attention, respect, and openness for mutual understanding.

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